

Application of a chelating resin containing imidazole-4,5-dicarboxylic acid in chromium speciation

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The work describes a procedure of preconcentration and separation of the two forms of chromium, viz. Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} in natural water by applying a solid phase extractor containing imidazole-4,5-dicarboxylic acid moiety anchored by -N=N- to a polystyrene divinylbenzene (8%) matrix. The sorption capacity of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} on this resin was found to be 0.41 and 1.12 mmol g⁻¹ at pH 6.0 and 1.0, respectively. The sorption of both the forms of chromium by the resin follows a second order rate law with rate constant values of 0.013 and 0.100 mmol⁻¹ min⁻¹ for Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} respectively. The recovery of both the forms of the chromium was quantitative by using 4 M HCl at a flow rate 1.0 ml min⁻¹. The proposed method has been applied successfully for the separation of chromium species present in ng ml⁻¹ level in natural water sample.

Chemical speciation of various trace element has received much attention in recent years because some elements even at the trace or ultratrace level have different physicochemical or biological properties and functions. For example, Cr^{VI} compounds have long been recognized as a carcinogen¹ whereas Cr^{III} compounds are potentially non-toxic. This means that only the determination of the total content of chromium in the sample is not sufficient to elucidate chemical or biological functions in environmental chemistry and toxicology. Chromium emissions to the environment are predominantly derived from fuel combustion, waste incineration and industrial processes². It is well established that the reduction of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} by enzymes results in the formation of reactive intermediates that contribute to the cytotoxicity, genotoxicity and carcinogenicity of Cr^{VI} containing compounds³. Recently various authors reviewed the toxic effect of hexavalent chromium on microorganism, plant and human health⁴.

Chromium speciation depends on the factors like redox potential and the pH of the media, viz. above pH 7, Cr^{III} predominates, and below pH 6, Cr^{VI} is the major species⁵. Chromate and cationic hydroxo-complexes are the two major forms of chromium present in natural water^{6,7}. So it is important to know the individual species of chromium in natural water, waste water or drinking water⁸. Low chromium levels are usually determined by separation of one specific form by sorption⁹, solvent extraction¹⁰ or coprecipitation^{7,11} followed by instrumental analysis. The second form is then determined, after it has been reduced or oxidized, as the

residual chromium content in the solution¹².

Solid phase extraction is a popular technique for the preconcentration and separation of trace metal ions. Separation and preconcentration of chromium species have been carried out by using polyimine Detata sorbent¹³, anionic solid exchanger¹⁴, solid phase resin^{15,16} and by biosorption¹⁷. Nevertheless, the report on the use of solid phase resin for pH-dependent speciation followed by selective elution of different forms of chromium, viz. Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} is scarce^{13,16}. We have reported earlier the synthesis of resin containing imidazole¹⁸, benzimidazole¹⁹, naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid¹⁶ and 6-mercaptopurine²⁰ in a polystyrene bed which have been used for the preconcentration and separation of heavy metal ions.

The present work describes the preconcentration and separation of the two forms of chromium, viz. Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} by using a solid phase extractor containing imidazole-4,5-dicarboxylic acid as a functional group anchored by azo function (-N=N-) to the polystyrene-divinylbenzene (Fig. 1), and finally determination of these two forms by flame atomic absorption spectrometry (FAAS) using nitrous oxide-acetylene flame.

Fig. 1. Imidazole-4,5-dicarboxylic acid anchored resin.

Results and discussion

Sorption and elution of metal ions :

Using batch method, the sorption behavior of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} on the resin was studied and the results are shown in Fig. 2. For Cr^{III} the sorption capacity increases with increasing pH, reaching a limiting value of 0.41 mmol g⁻¹ at pH 6.0, whereas for Cr^{VI} it is reversed and the maximum value has been found to be 1.12 mmol g⁻¹ at pH 1.0. At lower pH, the nitrogen atom of azo group is protonated^{21,22}

Fig. 2. Exchange capacities of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} on the resin vs pH.

and subsequently binds Cr^{VI}. The sorption of Cr^{III} at higher pH may be due to chelation by azo function and carboxylic groups. Thus there is a possibility of separating these two species of chromium from each other by simple pH adjustment. The effect of different eluents on the desorption of metal ion is given in Table 1. Complete elution of both the species took place with 10 ml of 4 M HCl.

Table 1. Desorption of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} by different eluents

Eluents	% Recovery	
	Cr ^{III}	Cr ^{VI}
<i>M</i>		
0.01 HCl	12.9	17.0
0.1 HCl	18.4	48.6
1 HCl	35.2	38.7
2 HCl	62.0	71.4
4 HCl	98.7	98.3
0.01 HNO ₃	19.0	14.1
0.1 HNO ₃	31.8	64.4
1 HNO ₃	63.4	82.8
2 HNO ₃	98.3	88.5

Kinetic parameters :

According to Frost and Pearson²³, the rate of exchange of metal ion by a chelating resin is controlled by a second order kinetic equation. Turse and Rieman²⁴ determined the rate of metal ions exchange of chelate forming resin by the following equation :

$$\ln Z = 2kQ_0(Q_0 - Q_\alpha)t/Q_\alpha$$

where $Z = [Q_t(Q_0 - 2Q_\alpha) + Q_0Q_\alpha]/Q_0(Q_\alpha - Q_t)$

The rate constant (*k*) is calculated from the slope (*S*) which is given by

$$S = 2kQ_0(Q_0 - Q_\alpha)/Q_\alpha$$

where Q_t is the amount (mmol) of metal ion exchanged at time *t*, Q_α the maximum exchange capacity at equilibrium and Q_0 the amount of chelating resin, in terms of mmol of Na⁺ exchanged after 24 h. A plot of ln *Z* vs *t* should be linear through zero for a second order exchange. The values of *S* and *k* obtained from the plot are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Kinetic parameters of exchange rates of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} with imidazole-4,5-dicarboxylic acid resin

Parameter	Cr ^{III}	Cr ^{VI}
pH	6.0	1.0
Q_0 (mmol g ⁻¹)	1.38	1.38
Q_α (mmol g ⁻¹)	0.41	1.12
<i>S</i>	0.082	0.064
<i>K</i> (mmol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	0.013	0.100

Table 3. Separation of 2 μg ml⁻¹ each of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} from several binary mixtures in a sample volume of 50 ml at pH 6.0 and 1.0 respectively

Ion ^a	% Recovery	
	Cr ^{III}	Cr ^{VI}
Al ³⁺	106.3	-
Fe ³⁺	96.1	-
V ⁴⁺	103.4	-
Cd ²⁺	97.2	-
Ni ²⁺	105.1	-
Co ²⁺	102.3	-
Zn ²⁺	97.0	-
VO ₃ ⁻	-	93.0
PO ₄ ³⁻	-	101.7
AsO ₂ ⁻	-	94.9
AsO ₄ ³⁻	-	101.5
MoO ₄ ²⁻	-	100.6
WO ₄ ²⁻	-	98.7

^aIn each case, the amount of foreign ion added was 2000 μg.

Effect of diverse ions :

Separation of 2 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ each of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} from several binary mixtures was carried out (Table 3). The presence of macro amounts of diverse metal ions like first transition series did not interfere. Elution of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} was achieved to the extent of almost 100% using suitable eluent as already described.

Application :

Separation of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} from the binary synthetic mixtures : Different amounts of each of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} were mixed in a total volume of 100 ml. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 1.0 from which Cr^{VI} was retained in the resin column while Cr^{III} not. In another set of experiment, pH was adjusted to 6.0 in which Cr^{III} was retained whereas Cr^{VI} not. Both Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} were eluted with 4 M HCl and the concentration was measured as described earlier. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Separation of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} in binary synthetic mixtures

No. of observation	Amounts taken	Amounts found	% error
	μg	μg	
1.	Cr^{III} : 100	Cr^{III} : 96.1	3.9
	Cr^{VI} : 100	Cr^{VI} : 102.7	2.7
2.	Cr^{III} : 120	Cr^{III} : 127.8	4.6
	Cr^{VI} : 60	Cr^{VI} : 59.1	2.6
3.	Cr^{III} : 50	Cr^{III} : 48.7	2.6
	Cr^{VI} : 100	Cr^{VI} : 104.2	4.2
4.	Cr^{III} : 10	Cr^{III} : 9.6	4.0
	Cr^{VI} : 100	Cr^{VI} : 101.2	1.2
5.	Cr^{III} : 100	Cr^{III} : 103.5	3.5
	Cr^{VI} : 10	Cr^{VI} : 10.4	4.0

Analysis of real water samples : The waste water samples, collected at three different points of Tannery industries, Kolkata, were filtered through a 0.45 μm Millipore membrane filter. Taking 350 ml of the filtrate the pH was maintained at 1.0 and the solution was passed through the resin column. In another portion of the filtrate (350 ml), the pH was adjusted to 6.0 and fed into the column. The retained species, viz. Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} were eluted by 10 ml 4 M HCl and the concentration of each species was measured. The results of the analysis of different species present in different natural water samples are presented in Table 5 and the results are compared with earlier developed method¹⁶.

Table 5. Determination of different species of chromium in natural water*

Sampling station	Chromium species found (ng ml^{-1})	
	Reference method ^a	Proposed method
1.	Cr^{III} : 620.2 \pm 3.3	Cr^{III} : 624.2 \pm 2.2
	Cr^{VI} : 296.5 \pm 2.1	Cr^{VI} : 302.1 \pm 1.1
2.	Cr^{III} : 660.5 \pm 3.5	Cr^{III} : 678.2 \pm 2.3
	Cr^{VI} : 440.2 \pm 2.3	Cr^{VI} : 445.4 \pm 1.2
3.	Cr^{III} : 529.4 \pm 2.3	Cr^{III} : 533.6 \pm 2.2
	Cr^{VI} : 260.4 \pm 1.5	Cr^{VI} : 267.8 \pm 1.1

*Average of five determinations. ^aRef. 16.*Conclusion :*

The application of this chelating resin offers an excellent means of trace chromium preconcentration and mutual separation of the various species, viz. Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} from natural water. The main advantage of this technique is that various species can be separated just by pH adjustment. The proposed method is simple, rapid and low-cost.

Experimental

A GBC Avanta atomic absorption spectrometer was used for absorbance measurement with the following conditions for chromium : lamp current 6 mA, wavelength 357.9 nm. A 0.45 μm pore size Millipore membrane filter was used for the filtration of natural water samples.

Potassium dichromate and chromium nitrate (both A. R., B.D.H.) were used as provided. The standard solution of Cr^{III} for AAS measurement was obtained from E. Merck (Germany). The diverse metal ion solutions were prepared from analytical grade reagents.

Preparation of the resin : Air-dried polystyrene DVB (8%) copolymer (5 g, 30–60 mesh) was nitrated with 18 M H_2SO_4 (25 ml) and 15 M HNO_3 (10 ml) by stirring the mixture at 60° for 1 h. The nitrated resin was then refluxed with a mixture of SnCl_2 (40 g), 12 M HCl (45 ml) and ethanol (50 ml) and refluxed for 20 h at 120° to obtain the amino resin, which was then diazotised by 1 M NaNO_2 and 1 M HCl at 0–5°. The diazotised resin was then treated with a basic solution of imidazole-4,5-dicarboxylic acid (3.5 g). The dark brown resin (Fig. 1) was filtered, dried in air and preserved at room temperature²⁵.

pH dependence studies : Taking metal ion in excess to the imidazole-4,5-dicarboxylic acid resin, exchange capacities were determined in the pH range 1.0–9.0. To the resin (100 mg) excess metal ion solution was added. The lower pH was adjusted with 0.1 M HCl whereas the higher pH by an aqueous solution of sodium acetate. After filtration,

the metal loaded resin was eluted by 4 M HCl and the concentration of the metal ion was measured in the effluent by FAAS using nitrous oxide-acetylene flame.

Kinetic studies : Kinetic parameters were determined for the sorption of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} on imidazole-4,5-dicarboxylic acid resin using batch technique. The concentrations of both the ions were measured by AAS at different time intervals at a particular pH in which exchange capacity was maximum.

Desorption studies : The resin containing maximum sorbed chromium ions was shaken with various eluting agents, viz. 0.01–2 M HCl or HNO₃ (30 ml) for 24 h. After desorption, the concentration of each chromium species was determined as usual.

Column operation : A glass column with (10 mm × 130 mm) was used. Air-dried resin (1.0 g) was immersed in double-distilled water and allowed to swell for 24 h. The column was then packed with fully swollen beads. The resin bed was thoroughly washed with 10 bed volumes of sodium acetate buffer of appropriate pH.

In the presence of various diverse metal ions the sorption and recovery characteristics for Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} were thoroughly examined. A 100 ml portion of the mixture of the test metal ion was allowed to flow through the resin column at a flow rate of 1.0 ml min⁻¹. The metal ion not sorbed was completely washed out using sodium acetate buffer of appropriate pH. The sorbed Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} were completely eluted with 4 M HCl and the concentration was measured as described earlier.

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